

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**PASSIVE SMOKING AND EFFECT OF NICOTINE LEVELS ON
PREGNANCY OUTCOMES**Dr. Hira Sial¹, Dr. Rabiya Razzaq², Dr. Rashida Hanif³²Faisalabad Medical University**Article Received:** September 2020 **Accepted:** October 2020 **Published:** November 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: The term "passive smoking" usually refers to the inhalation of smoke that is either exhaled by a smoker or released as side stream smoke from a burning cigarette. **Objective:** The main objective of the study is analyses the passive smoking and nicotine levels of pregnancy outcomes in infant health. **Material and methods:** This cross sectional study was conducted in Faisalabad Medical University during 2019 to 2020. The data was collected from 100 pregnant females who visited the OPD of hospital. The data was collected through a questionnaire. This questionnaire include the demographic data of all the participants. **Results:** The data was collected from 100 pregnant females who were second hand smokers. These women were non-smoker pregnant women and exposed to cigarette smoking and suffer from complications during childbirth. The mean age of mothers, was 27.38 ± 5.5 years (range from 13 to 45 years). **Conclusion:** It is concluded that non-smoking pregnant women in Pakistan who lived with a smoking husband were highly exposed to SHS, especially from their husbands.

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Please cite this article in press Hira Sial et al, *Passive Smoking And Effect Of Nicotine Levels On Pregnancy Outcomes.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(11).

INTRODUCTION:

The term "passive smoking" usually refers to the inhalation of smoke that is either exhaled by a smoker or released as sidestream smoke from a burning cigarette. Another name for passive smoking is "involuntary smoking," because the person who inhales it often has no choice in the matter. The effect of cigarettes on the pregnant woman and developing fetus are numerous with a wide range of sequelae that will remain with the fetus for the rest of her life. Smoking during pregnancy is associated with various adverse effects on pregnancy and fetal development, carries a lot of serious complications such as spontaneous abortion, placental abruption, and reduced birth weight of the newborn. Children of smoking mothers have an increased risk of premature birth, low birth weight, sudden infant death syndrome and respiratory diseases during infancy¹. Smoking also causes long-term risk of maternal health problems such as: heart disease, cancer, emphysema, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and higher mortality rate². Because women are more likely to quit smoking during pregnancy than at any other time, there are attempts to increase motivation and help them to stop smoking at the procreative phase of their life³. There is growing concern surrounding potential adverse reproductive health effects and pregnancy outcomes resulting from exposure to second-hand tobacco smoke⁴. Although exposure to second-hand tobacco smoke is preventable, it remains prevalent. The majority of second-hand tobacco smoke is in the form of side stream smoke generated from the burning end of a lighted cigarette, whereas the remainder is composed of mainstream smoke exhaled by individuals actively smoking⁵. Both mainstream and side stream smoke contain thousands of compounds many of them are harmful to humans⁶⁻⁷.

Objective

The main objective of the study is to analyse the passive smoking and nicotine levels of pregnancy outcomes in infant health.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in Faisalabad Medical University during 2019 to 2020. The data was collected from 100 pregnant females who visited the OPD of hospital. The data was collected through a questionnaire. This questionnaire includes the demographic data of all the participants. The self-administered questionnaire included medical and lifestyle variables, such as demographics, ages of both male and female partner, medical and reproductive history, smoking history and duration of infertility. Clinical pregnancy was determined by ultrasound visualization of a gestational sac and a fetal heartbeat. The samples, based on exposure to cigarette smoking, were divided into two groups: passive smoking-exposed and control groups and outcomes of maternal and neonatal complications, (Preterm Delivery, gestational age, rupture of membranes before the onset of labor, or up to 37 weeks of gestation (PROM), Stillbirth, Baby's head circumference, birth weight and length) in two groups were compared.

Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed with SPSS 17.0 software (Chicago, IL). Results are reported as median, geometric mean or numbers with percentages.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 100 pregnant females who were second hand smokers. These women were non-smoker pregnant women and exposed to cigarette smoking and suffer from complications during childbirth. The mean age of mothers, was 27.38 ± 5.5 years (range from 13 to 45 years). The mean number of pregnancies was 1.91 ± 0.99 (range from 1 to 5). The mean parity was 1.77 ± 0.84 (range from 0 to 5). 14.2% (213) of women were SHS exposure during pregnancy and 85.8% (1287) were not.

Factor	SHS	Non-exposed	P-values
Preterm Delivery	27.2	12.3	<0.001
PROM	38.13 ± 1.54	38.84 ± 1.31	<0.001
Mean G.A	27.38 ± 5.5	29.38 ± 2.8	<0.001
Stillbirth	27.9	0.2	1.00

The mean number of cigarettes smoked by the partners of pregnant women was 12.5 ± 7.7 (range from 5 to 40 cigarettes per day). The gestational age, in SHS exposure group, on average was 38.14 weeks (SD = ± 1.55) and in non-SHS exposure group, was 38.85 weeks (SD = ± 1.32). This difference was statistically significant (p-value < 0.001). This means, exposure to cigarette smoke effects on gestational age (Table 1). The mean length of infants, in SHS exposure group was 48.69 ± 1.88 and in non-SHS exposure group, was 49.42 ± 213 . This difference was

statistically significant (p - value < 0.001). This means, exposure to cigarette smoke effects on baby's length (Table 2).

	Passive smoker	Non passive smoker	P value
Baby's head circumference(cm)	33.42 \pm 1.23	33.88 \pm 1.45	<0.001
birth weight (g)	2996.19 \pm 354.35	3236.46 \pm 413.32	<0.001
Birth length(cm)	45.69 \pm 1.88	46.42 \pm 2.13	<0.001

DISCUSSION:

The high prevalence of SHS exposure for the non-smoking pregnant women in our provincial study (75%) is consistent with previous literature described 10 years ago in the city of Guangzhou. Although one study in the U.S.A. reported that 16.4% of non-smoking singleton pregnancies had SHS exposure during pregnancy, certain subpopulations even in developed countries like the U.S.A. may have high SHS exposure rates⁸. Among pregnant women in New Haven, Connecticut, U.S.A., 52% of nonsmokers had been classified as having had recent SHS exposure according to their urinary cotinine levels⁹. Another study examined correlates of SHS avoidance in a population of African-American pregnant non-smokers who lived with smokers and reported 73% of the women's salivary cotinine levels exceeded the passive smoking cut-off of 10 ng/ml¹⁰.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that non-smoking pregnant women in Pakistan who lived with a smoking husband were highly exposed to SHS, especially from their husbands. In addition, non-smoking pregnant women have inadequate knowledge on the harms of SHS. These findings are particularly significant for rural women.

REFERENCES:

1. Meysamie A, Ghaletaki R, Haghazali M, et al. Pattern of tobacco use among the Iranian adult population: results of the national Survey of Risk Factors of Non-Communicable Diseases (SuRFNCD-2007). *Tob Control*. 2010;19(2):125-128.
2. Ding YS, Trommel JS, Yan XJ, Ashley D, Watson CH. Determination of 14 polycyclic

aromatic hydrocarbons in mainstream smoke from domestic cigarettes. *Environ Sci Technol*. 2005;39(2):471-478.

3. Yang G, Fan L, Tan J, Qi G, Zhang Y, Samet JM, et al. Smoking in China: findings of the 1996 National Prevalence Survey. *JAMA*. 1999;282:1247-53.
4. Han JX, Gan DK, Zhai GR, Shi Y. Case control study on effect of passive smoking during different pregnancy term on small-for-gestational-age infants at term. *Wei Sheng Yan Jiu*. 2006;35:788-90.
5. Han JX, Gan DK, Zhai GR, Shi Y. A case-control study of risk factors of low birth weight at term. *Wei Sheng Yan Jiu*. 2004;33:483-5.
6. Venners SA, Wang XB, Chen CZ, Wang LH, Chen DF, Guang WW, et al. Paternal smoking and pregnancy loss: a prospective study using a biomarker of pregnancy. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2004;159:993-1001.
7. Hu PC, Liu SR. A case-control study on the risk factors for preterm delivery. *Hunan Yi Ke Da Xue Xue Bao*. 2000;25:446-8.
8. Zhang J, Ratcliffe JM. Paternal smoking and birthweight in Shanghai. *Am J Public Health*. 1993;83:207-10.
9. Zhang J, Cai WW. Risk factors associated with antepartum fetal death. *Early Hum Dev*. 1992;28:193-200.
10. Kwok MK, Schooling CM, Ho LM, Leung SL, Mak KH, McGhee SM, et al. Early life second-hand smoke exposure and serious infectious morbidity during the first 8 years: evidence from Hong Kong's "Children of 1997" birth cohort. *Tob Control*. 2008;17:263-70.